

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Complexes of Alizarin-Red-S with Neodymium and Praseodymium Ions

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Alizarin-red-S interacts with Neodymium (III) ions and Praseodymium (III) ions to form pink complexes which have been studied spectrophotometrically. The wavelength of maximum absorption for the dye and the complex were 420 and 530 $m\mu$ for both the complexes at $pH = 4.5$. The concentration ranges, in which Lambert and Beer's law is applicable have been ascertained. The ratio in which the rare-earth salts and the dye react to form the complexes have been found to be 1 : 2 by Jobs method, molar ratio method and slope ratio method. The log of formation constant of the complexes have been determined by non-equimolar method, equimolar method and mole ratio method. $\log k$ values are found to be 9.21 and 9.34 in praseodymium and neodymium respectively.

Coloured complexes of various metals with Alizarin-red-S have been reported by many workers¹⁻³. Analytical estimation of some rare-earths (La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Eu and Tb) and Y by spectrophotometric method was reported by Robert W. Rinehart⁴. The above

Fig. 1. Absorption-Spectra.
A. Alizarin-Red-S
B. Neodymium complex of the dye.

1. H. A. Liebhaafsky and E. H. Winslow. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 1776.
2. Larson and Hirezawa, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1956, **63**, 198.
3. S. V. Raghava Rao and Coworkers, *Anal. Chem. Acta.*, 1955, **13** 79, 142.
4. Robert W. Rinehart, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, **26**, 1820-2.

authors did not study the nature of the complexes formed and the stability constants with the rare earths. Recently in 1966, M. K. Akhemedi, D. A. Efendieu and S. R. Alieva⁵, determined ratio and stability constant of the praseodymium-complex. But the results obtained in this laboratory were not confirming the ratio mentioned and the stability constant by the above authors. Therefore the present work has been taken for detailed study.

Fig. 2. Job's Method for composition.
A. Concentration : 2×10^{-4}
B. " ; 1×10^{-4}

EXPERIMENTAL

Praseodymium and Neodymium chloride solutions of approximately $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ (A. R. Samples. Chemistry Division, A.E.E., Bombay) were prepared by dissolving them in double distilled water. The solutions were standardised gravimetrically, by precipitating as oxalate and then ignited as oxide. Solution of the Alizarin-red-S (B.D.H. Analar) was also prepared by dissolving weighed quantity in conductivity water. All studies were carried out by subsequent dilution of the solutions of metal and ligand.

Fig. 3. Molar Ratio Method.

Absorbance measurements were carried out with spectromom-20-spectrophotometer (Hungarian make) with 10 m.m. transmission-glass cells. The pH measurements of the solutions were recorded with Beckman pH meter model H-2 with glass and calomel electrodes

5. M. K. Akhemedi, D. A. Efendieu and S. R. Alieva, *Uch. Zap. Azerb. Gos. Univ. Ser. Khim. Nauk*, 1965(1), 3-10 (Russ.).

with an accuracy of 0.05 *pH*. The *pH* of the solutions were adjusted by the addition of dilute solutions of ammonium hydroxide or acetic acid. All measurements were carried out at room temperature.

Effect of time on the stability of the colour : The solution of the dye is fairly stable for 3 to 4 days, but when the metal and dye is mixed, the colour development of the complex is instantaneous and is stable upto 1 hr. It shows a gelatinous precipitate after standing for nearly 4 hrs. The reaction is fast and therefore, all the measurements have been taken within 1 hr. after mixing the solutions of metal and ligand.

Fig. 4. Job's Method for Stability. A. 1×10^{-4} M, $P = 2$
(Non-equimolar Solution Method) B. 5×10^{-5} M, $P = 4$

Nature of the complex : Vosburgh and Cooper's⁶ method was employed to determine the nature of the complex formed. The result shows that the maximum absorption of the Alizarin-red-S is at $420 \text{ m}\mu$ and that of the complexes at $530 \text{ m}\mu$ as also reported by W. Rinehart. It was observed that only one absorption maximum under all ratios of mixing and varying hydrogen ion concentrations, in both the cases indicating the formation of one complex. The measurements were carried out at $pH = 4.5$ and wavelength $530 \text{ m}\mu$. Lambert's and Beer's law was found to hold good up to the concentration 10γ .

Fig. 5. Stability Constant by Job's Method A : 2×10^{-4} M, $P = 1$
(Equimolar Solution Method) B : 1×10^{-4} M, $P = 1$

Stoichiometric ratios of the complexes of praseodymium and neodymium were determined by Job's method of continuous variation⁷, Molar ratio method⁸ and Slope ratio method⁹ which confirms the formation of 1 : 2 (M.L.) ratio.

Stability constant : The stability constants have been evaluated by three different methods *e.g.* non-equimolar method of Job, equimolar method used by Banerji and Dey¹⁰ and mole ratio method. The value of $\log K$ in this system of praseodymium and neodymium—Alizarin-red-S was found to be 9.21 and 9.34 respectively.

The ratio of 1 : 1 (M.L.) and the $\log$ of stability constant 5.84 (at $pH = 6.6$) of Alizarin-red-S complex with praseodymium reported by M. K. Akhmedhi, D. A. Efendieu and S. R. Alieva, was different than what is reported in this paper. This can be attributed to the slight precipitation observed at the $pH = 6.6$ and the close proximity of the wavelength of absorption of complex and ligand.

The following tentative structure can be given to the complexes :—

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